

Assessing the Impact of Post-Exposure Prophylaxis on Hepatitis B Vertical Transmission in Duhok City, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Nawfal R. Hussein

Department of Biomedical Sciences, College of Medicine, University of Zakho, Zakho Independent Administration, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Halder J. Abozait

Department of Medicine, College of Medicine, University of Duhok, Duhok, Kurdistan Region, Iraq

Abstract

Hepatitis B remains a significant global public health issue, with 296 million people living with chronic infection. Chronic infection can progress to cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma, causing 1.1 million deaths annually. The burden of hepatitis B is particularly high in developing countries, including Iraq, where high rates of vertical transmission contribute to the disease's prevalence. This study evaluates the effectiveness of post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) against vertical transmission of hepatitis B in Duhok city, Kurdistan region of Iraq. A total of 44 pregnant women with chronic hepatitis B were included. All infants received hepatitis B immune globulin (HBIG) within 24 hours of birth, followed by the hepatitis B vaccine at birth, 2, and 6 months of age. At 7 months, none of the infants tested positive for HBsAg, and all demonstrated protective levels of hepatitis B surface antibodies (HBsAb >100 IU/L). These findings indicate a high success rate of the implemented PEP regimen and endorse the continued use of PEP as an effective strategy for preventing vertical transmission of hepatitis B and providing strong immunity in the infants. Future study should further investigate the effectiveness of additional preventive measures and calls for broader implementation of similar protocols in other regions.

Introduction

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection remains a global public health problem with 296 million people living with chronic infection in 2023 [1,2]. Chronic infection can progress to liver cirrhosis, liver failure and hepatocellular carcinoma accounting for 1.1 million deaths due to hepatitis B in 2022 [2,3]. The infection is particularly common among developing countries and have been documented at high levels in the Duhok city in Iraq [4-6]. Most of the burden of chronic hepatitis B is ascribed to infection in early years of life. The risk of acquiring the virus from vertical transmission ranges from 90% among pregnant women with positive hepatitis B e-antigen (HBeAg) to 10% among those with negative HBeAg [7]. The younger the age at the time of acquiring the virus, the greater the chance of developing chronic hepatitis B – the risk is 90% in those infected as neonates, 30% among children infected at 1 - 4 years old and less than 5% among those infected as adults [3]. WHO recommends screening of all pregnant

women for hepatitis B surface-antigen (HBsAg), at least once and as early as possible during pregnancy. Infected mothers should be further tested for HBeAg and viral load to identify the risk of transmission [3]. Although vaccination is effective in more than 95% of individuals and is recommended for all neonates [8], the high prevalence of hepatitis B among pregnant women necessitates additional preventive measures [8]. These measures include: tenofovir treatment in HBsAg positive-mothers if HBeAg is positive or viral load is more than 200 000 IU/mL; and post-exposure prophylaxis (PEP) of newborns of HBsAg positive-mothers regardless of other markers by co-administration of hepatitis B immune globulin (HBIG) and hepatitis B vaccine [2,9]. PEP reduces the risk of vertical transmission from 90% to 5 -10%, thus providing efficient means of reducing the burden of hepatitis B in the whole population [8]. The effectiveness of PEP has not been well studied in Iraq. This study aims to determine the effectiveness of PEP

More Information

How to cite this article: Hussein NR, Abozait HJ. Assessing the Impact of Post-Exposure Prophylaxis on Hepatitis B Vertical Transmission in Duhok City, Kurdistan Region, Iraq. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2025;3(4):93-5.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(4).16

Keywords:

Hepatitis B,
Post-exposure prophylaxis,
HBIG,
Kurdistan region,
Iraq.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

against the vertical transmission of hepatitis B infection in Duhok city, Kurdistan region of Iraq.

Materials and Methods

Women who attended Duhok Maternity Hospital from January 2022 to January 2025 were tested for HBsAg, anti-hepatitis C antibody (HCV-Ab), human immunodeficiency virus antibodies (HIV-Ab 1 and HIV-Ab 2) [10]. Those who tested positive for HBsAg were further tested for anti-hepatitis B core-IgG (anti-HBc IgG), HBeAg and hepatitis B viral load. Similar to a prior study [12], ELISA was used to detect antigens and antibodies while viral load was determined by RTPCR. In this period, we identified 44 pregnant women who were positive for HBsAg. According to the hospital's policy, all 44 newborns were given HBIG within 24 hours and hepatitis B vaccine series at birth, 2 and 6 months of age. All infants were then tested for HBsAg and anti-hepatitis B surface-antibody (HBsAb) titers at the age of 7 months to determine the success rate and need for further vaccination. Studies have documented that low-responders (HBsAb titers 10 – 100 IU/L) may still acquire infection and lose the titer with time thus a higher threshold (titers more than 100 IU/L) were regarded as sufficient-responders [13]. Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study.

Results

The mothers ranged in age from 17 to 40 years, with a mean age of 28.3 ± 5.7 years. Most of them (59.1%) were in their twenties, while 11.4% were aged 20 or younger. A total of 56.8% delivered female infants and 43.2% delivered males. Characteristics and results of investigations of mothers are presented in table 1. All mothers were confirmed to be HBsAg and anti-HBc IgG positive, demonstrating that the entire group has a chronic HBV infection. HBeAg was found to be positive in only 6.8% of mothers, a finding that suggests a lowered likelihood of active viral replication in the majority of cases. Only 4.5% of the mothers had a viral load surpassing 200,000 IU/mL, a threshold usually associated with an elevated risk of vertical transmission. Notably, 15.9% showed undetectable viral loads. A total of 44 infants born to mothers with chronic HBV infection were monitored and assessed at 7 months of age. Serological tests showed that none of the infants had detectable levels of HBsAg, confirming that there was no vertical transmission of HBV. Additionally, all infants demonstrated protective levels of hepatitis B surface antibodies (HBsAb), with titers exceeding 100 IU/L. This consistently strong immune response indicates that the postnatal immunoprophylaxis approach was exceptionally effective in both genders.

Table 1: Characteristics of Mothers

Factors	Number	Percentage
Age (years)		
≤20	5	11.4%
21-30	26	59.1%
31-40	13	29.5%
Range	17 – 40	
Mean ± SD	28.32 ± 5.71	
HCV positive	0	0%
HIV positive	0	0%
HBsAg positive	44	100%
Anti-HBc IgG positive	44	100%
HBeAg		
Positive	3	6.8%
Negative	41	93.2%
Viral Load (IU/mL)		
Undetected	7	15.9%
< 10	9	20.5%
10 - 200 000	26	59.1%
> 200 000	2	4.5%
Product of delivery		
Female	25	56.8%
Male	19	43.2%

Discussion

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of post-exposure prophylaxis in prevention of vertical transmission of HBV infection in Duhok city, Kurdistan region of Iraq. Among a sample of 44 women with chronic HBV infection, no infants contracted HBV after receiving HBIG within 24 hours and hepatitis B vaccine at birth, 2 and 6 months of age and all the infants had HBsAb titer greater than 100 IU/L. It is important to mention that 3 mothers (6.8%) had a positive HBeAg since it is associated with significantly higher rate of vertical transmission of hepatitis B [7]. These three patients were started on tenofovir treatment in the third trimester of pregnancy. Maternal HIV coinfection has also been associated with a higher risk of vertical transmission of hepatitis B but our sample had no cases of coinfection with HIV [6]. Our results further support a previous study in the same region in 2015 where out of 95 pregnant women with chronic hepatitis B, 100% of infants had negative HBsAg and 98.9% achieved HBsAb titers greater than 10 IU/L after completing the prophylaxis course [14]. The results also align with prior studies from neighboring countries including Iran where 97.4% of infants had negative HBsAg and more than 94% achieved HBsAb greater than 10 IU/L and Saudi Arabia where 100% had negative HBsAg at the end of the study [15, 16].

Conclusion

This study confirms the effectiveness of prophylactic measures against vertical transmission of hepatitis B in Duhok city and indorses the incorporation of post-exposure prophylaxis into healthcare practices in other cities. This study has limitations; first, no comparison group was available to better understand the effect of preventive measures; second, the sample size was small. Future studies should focus on success rate of other preventive measures such as caesarean section or in other ages such as adults with needlestick injury.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Hsu Y-C, Huang DQ, Nguyen MH. Global burden of hepatitis B virus: current status, missed opportunities and a call for action. *Nature Reviews Gastroenterology & Hepatology*. 2023;20(8):524–37. doi: 10.1038/s41575-023-00760-9.
- [2] Huang ZH, Lu GY, Qiu LX, Zhong GH, Huang Y, Yao XM, Liu XH, Huang SJ, Wu T, Yuan Q, Wang YB, Su YY, Zhang J, Xia NS. Risk of hepatocellular carcinoma in antiviral treatment-naïve chronic hepatitis B patients treated with entecavir or tenofovir disoproxil fumarate: a network meta-analysis. *BMC Cancer*. 2022 Mar 17;22(1):287. doi: 10.1186/s12885-022-09413-7.
- [3] World Health Organization (WHO). Global hepatitis report 2024: action for access in low- and middle-income countries. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2024. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240091672>. Accessed May 20, 2025.
- [4] Hussein N, Abozait H, Naqid I, Ibrahim N, Khalid F, Musa D, et al. Risk Factors of Hepatitis B Virus Infection in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Mediterranean Journal of Hematology and Infectious Diseases*. 2025;17:e2025018. doi: 10.4084/2FMJHID.2025.018.
- [5] Hussein N. Risk factors of hepatitis B virus infection among blood donors in Duhok city, Kurdistan Region, Iraq. *babol-caspjim*. 2018;9(1):22–6. <http://dx.doi.org/10.22088/cjim.9.1.22>.
- [6] Hussein NR, Musa DH, Hawezy DJ, Ahmed FMR, Khalid FK, Naqid IA, et al. A study on the prevalence and the risk factors of hepatitis B virus infection in Kurdistan Region, Iraq: A multicenter study. *Journal of Contemporary Medical Sciences*. 2021;7(5). doi: 10.22317/jcms.v7i5.1037.
- [7] di Filippo Villa D, Navas M-C. Vertical Transmission of Hepatitis B Virus—An Update. *Microorganisms*. 2023;11(5). doi: 10.3390/microorganisms11051140.
- [8] Pattyn J, Hendrickx G, Vorsters A, Van Damme P. Hepatitis B Vaccines. *The Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 2021;224(Supplement_4):S343–S51. doi: 10.1093/infdis/jiaa668.
- [9] OpenAnesthesia. Needle stick injury mgmt. OpenAnesthesia [homepage on the Internet]. Last updated 2015 Mar 05. [cited 2025 Jun 24]. Available from: https://www.openanesthesia.org/keywords/needle_stick_injury_mgmt/
- [10] Pfizer. Protocol: Safety, tolerability, pharmacokinetics, and pharmacodynamics of PF-06817024 in healthy participants, chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyps, and atopic dermatitis (Phase 1 study) [protocol]. *ClinicalTrials.gov*: NCT02743871. 2016 Apr 15 [cited 2025 Jun 24]. Available from: https://cdn.clinicaltrials.gov/large-docs/71/NCT02743871/Prot_000.pdf
- [11] Khalid FK, Rasheed NA, Hussein NR, Naqid IA. A study of HBV infection and its risk factors in pregnant women in Zakho city, Iraq. *PLOS ONE*. 2022;17(8):e0273362. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0273362.
- [12] Hussein N, Saleem Z, Ibrahim N, Assafi MS, Daniel S. The Prevalence of HBV Infection in Renal Transplant Recipients and the Impact of Infection on Graft Survival. *Acta Medica Iranica*. 2019;57(6). doi: 10.18502/acta.v57i6.1884.
- [13] Kakisaka K, Sakai A, Yoshida Y, Miyasaka A, Takahashi F, Sumazaki R, et al. Hepatitis B Surface Antibody Titers at One and Two Years after Hepatitis B Virus Vaccination in Healthy Young Japanese Adults. *Internal Medicine*. 2019;58(16):2349–55. doi: 10.2169/internalmedicine.2231-18.
- [14] S. Khalil A, L. Abdulkareem W, R. Hussein N. The Effectiveness of Post-Exposure Prophylaxis in Infants Born to Hepatitis B Virus Positive Mothers in the Kurdistan Region, Iraq. *Int J Infect*. 2016:e42412. doi: 10.5812/iji.42412.
- [15] Ahmadinejad Z, Abdi Liae Z, Salehizadeh S, Mansori S, Alijani N. Efficacy of Post-Exposure Prophylaxis in Infants Born to HBsAg Positive Mothers in Iran; Is It Authentic? *Iran J Pediatr*. 2016;In Press. doi: 10.5812/ijp.5979.
- [16] Al Qurashi M, Al-Najjar H, Aga SS, Mohammad H, Mustafa A, Al Hindi M, et al. The Efficacy of Post-Exposure Prophylaxis in Infants Born to HBsAg-Positive Mothers: A Single Center Experience in Saudi Arabia. *Global Pediatric Health*. 2024;11:2333794X241290780. doi: 10.1177/2333794X241290780.

